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1 **Sorption of chlorinated hydrocarbons from synthetic and natural groundwater by**
2 **organo-hydrotalcites: towards their applications as remediation nanoparticles**

3

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10

11 **Abstract**

12 Chlorinated hydrocarbons (CHCs) are recalcitrant compounds frequently found as contaminants in
13 groundwater. Hydrotalcites (HT) have emerged as promising sorbents due to their tunable properties
14 and anion exchange capacity. Here, two types of organo-HT were synthesized, via coprecipitation, by
15 intercalation of two different anionic surfactants, sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium 1-dodecane
16 sulfonate. These compounds were first characterized by a suite of techniques to quantify surfactant
17 intercalation and to evaluate their physico-chemical properties. Next, the sorption affinity of these
18 organo-HT towards a suite of CHCs was tested under various conditions, including interlayer
19 surfactant type, single and multiple CHCs systems, and different water chemistry (pH, ionic
20 composition). Sorption coefficients (K_d) and organic-matter-normalized partition coefficient (K_{om})
21 derived from linear sorption isotherms for individual CHC were inversely correlated to their
22 hydrophobicity in the order of: tetrachloroethylene > tetrachloromethane > trichloroethylene > 1,1,2-
23 trichloroethane > trichloromethane. K_{om} values were further affected by the organo-HT drying process.
24 In contrast, varying water chemistry and pH, and the co-existence of multiple CHCs had little effect
25 on K_{om} values, indicating that competition between CHCs and ionic strength have a marginal effect on
26 the sorption affinity. The inverse linear relationship between CHC hydrophobicity and K_{om} is shown
27 to be a suitable tool to predict organo-HT's sorption efficiency in complex CHC contaminated
28 groundwaters. Overall, organo-HT's might be used as potential sorbents for *ex situ* treatment of CHCs
29 in groundwater.

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30 **Keywords:** layered double hydroxide; contaminated groundwater; nanomaterials; sorption isotherms;
31 organic pollutants; solvents

32 1. Introduction

33 Chlorinated hydrocarbons (CHCs) account for almost 10% of the contaminants frequently found in
34 soil and groundwater across Europe (van Liedekerke et al., 2014). These hydrophobic organic
35 compounds were used extensively as solvents for metal degreasing, dry-cleaning, pharmaceutical
36 production, pesticides, adhesives, and refrigerants (Huang et al., 2014), leading to numerous events of
37 uncontrolled release into subsurface environments. The properties that have made CHCs attractive for
38 industrial purposes (e.g. stable under aerobic conditions, low flammability, low solubility in water,
39 low viscosity, and higher density than water), make them a real challenge when trying to remove them
40 from the subsurface (Sale et al., 2008). Furthermore, CHCs do not easily biodegrade under natural
41 conditions; thus, they are often found as contaminants of concern (COCs) in soil and groundwater.

42 For the past few decades, a wide variety of minerals have been used as sorbents for organic pollutants
43 in water (Cornejo and Celis, 2008; Rojas, 2012), including zeolites (Leal et al., 2017), organoclays
44 (Smith and Galan 1995; Gullick and Weber 2001), smectites (Lee et al., 2004), and layered double
45 hydroxides (LDH) (Ulibarri and Hermosin 2001; Bruna et al. 2006; Jobbágy and Regazzoni 2006;
46 Zaghouane-Boudiaf et al. 2011; Ruan et al. 2013; Zubair et al. 2017). LDH are a family of synthetic
47 and natural inorganic-lamellar hydroxide compounds with a high anionic exchange capacity
48 (calculated around 3 meq/g) (Rives, 2001). LDH have a tunable, brucite-like structure with the
49 general formula: $[M^{II}_{1-x}M^{III}_x(OH)_2]A_{x/n}^n \cdot mH_2O$ (Miyata 1983). Hydrotalcite-like (HT) compounds
50 are a specific group of LDH, composed of positively charged layers of edge-sharing $Mg(OH)_6$ and
51 $Al(OH)_6$ octahedra, that alternate with layers of inorganic anions (e.g. NO_3^- , Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , CO_3^{2-}) for
52 charge balance, and which also contain water. Organic anions such as aliphatic and aromatic sulfates
53 (You et al. 2002b), carboxylates (Newman and Jones, 1998), or cyclodextrins (Zhao and Vance, 1997)
54 can substitute for the inorganic anions in the HT interlayer (Clearfield et al., 1991), resulting in
55 organo-HT with hydrophobic properties, which increases their sorption affinity towards organic
56 pollutants such as CHCs (e.g., tetrachloroethylene (PCE), trichloroethylene (TCE) and 1,1,1

57 trichloroethane (1,1,1-TCA) (You et al. 2002a,b; Zhao and Nagy 2004). Zhao and Nagy (2004)
58 showed that HT (Mg/Al molar ratio = 3:1) with intercalated dodecyl sulfate (DS) forms an effective
59 partitioning medium for trapping CHCs. Similarly, Jobbágy and Regazzoni (2006) determined that
60 solute partitioning was the main sorption mechanism for aromatic compounds by 3:1 HT with
61 intercalated DS and the derived partition coefficients correlated linearly with the solubility (i.e.,
62 hydrophobicity) of the aromatic compounds. This linear relationship was also described for CHCs
63 sorption in soils (Chiou et al. 1979; Chiou 2002), and sorption of herbicides by organo-Mg/Fe LDH
64 (Ruan et al., 2013). The efficiency with which organo-HT can remove CHCs indicates that this
65 process has the potential for application in filters, membranes, or *in situ* permeable reactive barriers to
66 treat groundwater contaminated by CHCs.

67 CHC sorption by organo-HT has mainly been studied in simple, well controlled laboratory
68 experiments (You et al. 2002a, 2002b; Zhao and Nagy 2004). These studies provided some key
69 insights into the sorption capacities and mechanisms of organo-HT towards CHCs, however, they
70 have largely ignored the complexity of natural systems, such as varying water chemistry and pH.
71 Moreover, while natural attenuation processes can partly degrade the parent compounds in a spill (e.g.
72 PCE to TCE; tetrachloromethane (CT) to trichloromethane (TCM) (Lawrence, 2006), this often
73 creates a more complex and more toxic dissolved plume in the subsurface. Thus, to assess the
74 applicability of organo-HT for remediation of such complex CHCs plumes, it is necessary to
75 determine how the sorption capacity of organo-HT is affected by varying water chemistry and
76 importantly also by the coexistence of multiple CHCs.

77 The specific objectives of this study are: (a) to synthesize two types of organo-HT with interlayer DS
78 and dodecane sulfonate (1-DF) and characterize their size, structure, and composition; (b) to
79 determine the sorption affinity and extent of these organo-HT towards individual, common CHCs
80 contaminants (e.g. PCE, TCE, CT, TCM, and 1,1,2-trichloroethane (1,1,2-TCA)); (c) to assess if the
81 sorption coefficient (K_d) of these organo-HT changes in response to varying water chemistry, pH, and
82 the coexistence of multiple CHCs; and (d) to expose organo-HT to a complex contaminated
83 groundwater and compare measured and predicted sorption capacities. Overall, this data will help to

84 identify the optimal organo-HT compound and geochemical conditions for successful removal of
85 CHCs from contaminated groundwater.

86 2. Materials and methods

87 2.1 Synthesis of organo-HT

88 Reagent grade metal nitrates (99.9% of purity), ($\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$), and NaOH
89 were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Anionic surfactant salts, sodium dodecyl sulfate ($\text{NaC}_{12}\text{H}_{25}\text{SO}_4$)
90 ($\geq 98.5\%$ of purity) and sodium 1-dodecane sulfonate ($\text{NaC}_{12}\text{H}_{25}\text{SO}_3$) ($> 98.0\%$ of purity) were
91 purchased from Sigma Aldrich and TGI (Japan), respectively. Chemicals were used without further
92 purification. The structures and characteristics of the anionic surfactants are described in Table SM-1.
93 All glassware used in this study was first soaked in 3 M HCl solution overnight, thoroughly rinsed
94 with deionized water (MilliQ, resistivity $> 18 \Omega\text{cm}$), and dried at 75°C before use. All solutions
95 described below were prepared with CO_2 -free MilliQ, prepared by overnight sparging with N_2 .

96 Organo-HT with a Mg/Al molar ratio of 3:1 was synthesized by incorporating either DS or 1-DF into
97 the HT via co-precipitation (Clearfield et al., 1991), as illustrated in Figure SM-1 and described
98 below. The synthesis with 1-DF was performed at $40 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$ to enhance surfactant dissolution, while
99 for DS, it was done at room temperature. For the synthesis, 50 mL of the metal solution (0.75 M
100 $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 0.25 M $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$) were added dropwise (1-2 mL/min) to a beaker
101 containing 100 ml of surfactant solution (i.e., 0.25 M $\text{NaC}_{12}\text{H}_{25}\text{SO}_4$ or $\text{NaC}_{12}\text{H}_{25}\text{SO}_3$), while keeping
102 the pH constant at 9 by the addition of 1 M NaOH solution with a titrator system (Metrohm,
103 Tritando 809). Throughout synthesis, the suspension was thoroughly stirred and bubbled with pure N_2
104 gas to minimize CO_2 influx, i.e., intercalation of carbonate species. At the end of the titration, the
105 slurries were stirred for 1 h at room temperature, then centrifuged, and the supernatant decanted. The
106 wet paste was washed 4-5 times with deionized water until the supernatant was free of NO_3^- (Mohr
107 salt- H_2SO_4 test). The wet paste was either dried or used directly depending on experiment (Table 1,
108 section 2.4). The dried samples were ground with an agate mortar and pestle and stored in capped-
109 plastic bottles until use. In experiments where the wet paste was used directly, the paste was first

110 weighed and then dispersed into 100 mL of MilliQ and thoroughly stirred. Aliquots of this mixture
111 were then directly added to the sorption experiments. To quantify the concentration of organo-HT in
112 these suspensions, known aliquots were oven dried (75 °C) and then weighed (average of 4
113 replicates). From here on, we refer to the two synthesized organo-HT as Mg₃Al-DS and Mg₃Al-1-DF,
114 based on the intercalated anion. For comparison, 3:1 HT with interlayer carbonate (Mg₃Al-CO₃) was
115 also synthesized (details in the Supporting Information, Text S1).

116

117 2.2 Characterization of organo-HT

118 The synthesized organo-HT were analyzed by powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD), infrared
119 spectroscopy (FT-IR), induced couple plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES),
120 thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), scanning and transmission electron microscopy (SEM, TEM),
121 laser diffraction, and the Brunner-Emmett-Teller (BET) method, to assess crystal structure,
122 composition, and particle size. Detailed information on organo-HT sample preparation and analysis
123 procedures can be found in the Supporting Information (Text S1).

124

125 2.3 Pristine, contaminated, and synthetic groundwater

126 Four different waters were used in the sorption experiments: MilliQ, synthetic groundwater (SGW),
127 pristine natural groundwater (NGW), and contaminated groundwater (CGW). The last two were
128 collected from a subsurface sedimentary aquifer at an industrial site in Spain, upstream (NGW) and
129 close to an old spill (CGW), respectively. The main CHCs in the CGW were 1,1,2-TCA (55%), 1,1,2-
130 DCA (20%), TCM (8%), and TCE (5%). The NGW and CGW (pH: 7.8 ± 0.2, geochemistry in Table
131 SM-2) were kept refrigerated until use. The SGW (pH: 8.0 ± 0.2) was prepared based on the method
132 described by Smith et al. (2002), and is detailed in the Supporting Information (Text S1).

133

134 2.4 Sorption experiments for CHCs

135 Chlorinated hydrocarbons (CHCs) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich, with purities $\geq 97\%$ for 1,1,2-
136 TCA and $\geq 99.0\%$ for CT, TCM, PCE, and TCE. Methanol stock solutions for each CHC and a
137 mixture of TCE, TCM, and 1,1,2-TCA ($C_0=50$ mg/L) were prepared and kept refrigerated until use.
138 Table SM-1 summarizes the main characteristics and abbreviations of CHCs used in this study.

139 A large set of sorption isotherms (equilibration concentration (C_e) vs. amount sorbed (q_e)) were
140 determined using batch equilibration at 20 ± 1 °C (Table 1). For this, specific amounts of organo-HT
141 were placed into 20 mL glass vials and spiked with the corresponding CHC stock solution. The vials
142 were fully filled with MilliQ, SGW or NGW (Table 1) to minimize headspace, and then crimp-sealed
143 with Silicone-PTFE septa. The final solid-liquid ratio was 3.2 g/l and the CHC concentrations ranged
144 from 0-400 mg/L. Vials were placed upside-down (to minimize volatilization) on a shaker to
145 equilibrate for 24 h. Previous CHC sorption studies with Mg_3Al -DS have shown this to be a sufficient
146 equilibration time (You et al. 2002b; Zhao and Nagy 2004). The vials were then centrifuged, and 0.5
147 to 1 mL of the supernatant were transferred into 20 ml glass vials and crimp-sealed for headspace
148 analysis (section 2.5). Each experiment was performed in duplicate and controls without sorbent were
149 run in parallel.

150 We first evaluated the effect of interlayer surfactant type on CHC uptake, by determining sorption
151 isotherms for PCE and TCE in MilliQ by Mg_3Al -DS and Mg_3Al -1-DF (both dried at 75 °C following
152 synthesis). The impact of post-synthesis treatment on sorption capacity was determined in
153 experiments with TCE in MilliQ with Mg_3Al -DS (a) dried at 75 °C for 48 h, (b) freeze dried at -76 °C
154 (0.10 mbar, 24 h), and (c) used directly as a wet paste. In a second set of experiments, sorption
155 isotherms were determined for each individual CHC compound by Mg_3Al -DS (added as wet paste) in
156 MilliQ, as well as in ternary solute systems (with equal concentrations of TCE, TCM, and 1,1,2-TCA)
157 to test the effects of different water chemistry (MilliQ, SGW and NGW) and varying pH (6-11) (Table
158 1). For the pH experiments, the suspension pH was manually adjusted with HCl and NaOH and kept
159 constant for at least an hour, before starting the sorption experiment. The last set of sorption

160 experiments was performed with CGW in a slightly larger set-up, using 100 mL screw-cap vials to
161 which 0.35 g of Mg₃Al-DS was added.

162 2.5 CHCs analysis and sorption coefficient

163 CHCs were analyzed based on previous methods (Mangayayam et al. 2018) using gas
164 chromatography mass spectrometry (GC-MS) equipped with an automated headspace sampler (details
165 in the Supporting Information, text S1). The concentration of CHCs sorbed by organo-HT was
166 determined by subtracting the equilibrium concentration in the experiments from the one in the
167 control. This is done to account for potential septum sorption, volatilization losses, or experimental
168 errors. The amount of CHC sorbed (q_e) (mg of sorbate/g of sorbent) was determined by the following
169 equation:

$$170 \quad q_e = \frac{(C_0 - C_e) \cdot V}{m}, \quad (1)$$

171 where C_0 and C_e (mg/L) are initial and equilibrium concentrations of CHC in solution, V (L) is the
172 solution volume, and m (g) is the added sorbent mass. Sorption isotherms were obtained by plotting q_e
173 versus C_e (amount sorbed vs equilibrium concentration). The sorption coefficient (K_d) for each sorbate
174 was determined from a linear regression fit rationing q_e (mg/g) to C_e . Linear partition coefficients
175 have been shown to depend on the organic content of the sorbent (Chiou, 2002). We tested for this
176 here and normalized K_d values to the percentage of organic content OC (%) in the organo-HT
177 (estimated from TGA data) and calculated the organic-matter-normalized partition coefficient (K_{om}):

$$178 \quad K_{om} = K_d \times [100 \times f / \text{OC} (\%)], \quad (2)$$

179 where f corresponds to the fraction of carbon in the surfactant, i.e., weight of carbon in the surfactant
180 divided by the surfactant molecular weight (Jobbágy and Regazzoni, 2006).

181

182 3. Results and discussion

183 3.1 Physico-chemical properties of organo-HT

184 PXRD patterns showed the characteristic basal spacing (d_{003}) of 7.7 Å for Mg_3Al-CO_3 , (Miyata 1983;
185 Rives 2001), while for organo-HT intercalated with DS and 1-DF, the $d_{(003)}$ increased to 26.4 Å and
186 23.9 Å, respectively, in agreement with previous studies (Clearfield et al. 1991; Wang et al. 2005;
187 Bruna et al. 2006) (Figure SM-2). Considering a thickness of 4.8 Å for the brucite-like sheets (Miyata,
188 1975), the interlamellar distances for Mg_3Al-DS and $Mg_3Al-1-DF$ were 21.6 Å and 19.1 Å,
189 respectively; values very close to the chain lengths of these surfactants (Table SM-1). This suggested
190 a monolayer vertical arrangement for the DS molecules and a slightly tilted arrangement for 1-DF
191 molecules in the interlayer (Clearfield et al., 1991). The presence of the $d_{(110)}$ diffraction peak at 1.53
192 Å, corresponding to one half of dimension a (Rives 2001), confirmed the successful synthesis of a HT
193 phase. Similarly, FT-IR spectra of Mg_3Al-DS and $Mg_3Al-1-DF$ showed characteristic absorption
194 bands of a HT compound with strong bands at 500-800 cm^{-1} for metal-oxide-metal stretching modes
195 (Figure SM-3). Intercalation of surfactants was confirmed by the absorption bands at 1220, 1186,
196 1064, and 1050 cm^{-1} , which are characteristic modes of S=O antisymmetric and symmetric stretching,
197 C-H stretching (ca. 3000 cm^{-1}), and C-H bending (1469 cm^{-1}) (Wang et al. 2005; Bruna et al. 2006;
198 Zaghouane-Boudiaf et al. 2011) (Table SM-3). PXRD and FT-IR results were further corroborated by
199 chemical analyses of acid digested samples, which showed Mg/Al and Al/S ratios close to 3:1 and
200 1:1, respectively (Table SM-4). The organic content, OC (%) of the organo-HT was derived from
201 chemical analyses (Table SM-4). This yielded an approximate OC content of 28.4% for Mg_3Al-DS
202 and 31.4% for $Mg_3Al-1-DF$ (Table SM-5). In comparison to the theoretical OC content (as calculated
203 from their respective formula, Table SM-4), the OC content in Mg_3Al-DS and $Mg_3Al-1-DF$ was
204 slightly higher, by ~1% and 7%, respectively. This suggested that some surfactants also adsorbed to
205 the HT surface, rather than intercalated, which has also been observed in previous studies (You et al.
206 2002b; Narine and Guy 1981). These results could explain why some sodium was detected in the
207 $Mg_3Al-1-DF$ solids (Table SM-4), where some of the surfactant adsorbed to the surface charge

208 compensation (Clearfield et al., 1991). The OC and water contents were further confirmed by TGA
209 analyses (details in the Supporting Information, Figure SM-4 and Table SM-5).

210 In terms of organo-HT particle size and morphology, SEM and TEM images showed large particle
211 aggregates with sizes between 40 and 200 μm (Figure SM-5a), while individual organo-HT platelets
212 were nanometer sized (50 - 200 nm) with poorly defined edges (Figure SM-5b). The average cluster
213 size, as determined by laser diffraction, was $\sim 150 \mu\text{m}$. The specific surface area (S_{BET}) of $\text{Mg}_3\text{Al-DS}$
214 and $\text{Mg}_3\text{Al-1-DF}$ were 0.9 and 0.4 m^2/g , respectively, which agrees with previous studies (You et al.
215 2002b; Bruna et al. 2006). The surfactant intercalation drastically reduced the specific surface area
216 compared to the inorganic HT (45 m^2/g for $\text{Mg}_3\text{Al-CO}_3$ synthesized here) (Figure SM-6), which is
217 interpreted to be caused by the strong aggregation of these particles (Figure SM-5a), likely further
218 facilitated by the surface adsorbed surfactants. Other studies also reported on the strong aggregation
219 of $\text{Mg}_3\text{Al-DS}$ (Clearfield et al., 1991; You et al., 2002a) and $\text{Mg}_3\text{Al-1-DF}$ (Wang et al. 2005) and the
220 respective reduction in the specific surface area.

221 Overall, these characterization results showed that both organo-HT were successfully synthesized,
222 with properties similar to previous studies (Clearfield et al. 1991; Wang et al. 2005; You et al. 2002a).
223 Looking in more detail at the specific characteristics of these compounds, it seems that $\text{Mg}_3\text{Al-DS}$
224 could be more suitable for CHC sorption as DS intercalation seems more effective compared to DF
225 intercalation (i.e., less surface adsorbed). In terms of costs, $\text{Mg}_3\text{Al-DS}$ would also be the preferred
226 choice, as it is the cheaper compound to produce. Another observation that could be key for CHC
227 sorption is that these organo-HT compounds aggregate very strongly, particularly during intermediate
228 steps, i.e. drying (Figure SM-7), which potentially affects their sorption capacity. Based on these
229 considerations, we therefore set up some initial sorption experiments to determine the most effective
230 organo-HT and post-synthesis treatment.

231

232 3.2 Sorption experiment in single solute systems

233 3.2.1 Effect of organo-HT properties on sorption yield

234 First, we tested whether CHC sorption by organo-HT is affected by the intercalated surfactant type
235 (i.e., DS vs DF-1). Looking at the sorption isotherms for Mg₃Al-DS and Mg₃Al-1-DF (both dried the
236 same way) in experiments with either PCE or TCE (Figure 1a and Table SM-6), there were no
237 significant differences in log K_{om} values (log K_{om} PCE =3.03-3.03 and log K_{om} TCE =2.56-2.50 for
238 Mg₃Al-DS-Mg₃Al-1-DF, respectively). Similar log K_{om} values were reported for PCE (3.23) and TCE
239 (2.60) sorption by oven dried Mg₃Al-DS synthesized the same way as in this study (Zhao and Nagy,
240 2004). To the best of our knowledge, there is no data on CHC log K_{om} values for Mg₃Al-1DF to
241 compare with. Moreover, considering that Mg₃Al-1-DF surfaces were likely covered with excess
242 surfactant (more so than for Mg₃Al-DS), this did not seem to affect the observed sorption properties.
243 Overall, these results suggest that changing the functional group of the intercalated surfactant did not
244 majorly impact sorption affinity towards these CHCs.

245 Next, we tested the effect of post-synthesis drying on organo-HT sorption capacity, shown in Figure
246 1b. Slight differences were seen in the slope of the sorption isotherms, obtained for TCE by the two
247 differently dried Mg₃Al-DS and the untreated Mg₃Al-DS (i.e., not dried, Figure 1b). Specifically, log
248 K_{om} was highest for untreated Mg₃Al-DS (log K_{om} TCE=2.71), while drying seemed to decrease Mg₃Al-
249 DS sorption capacity (i.e., log K_{om}), particularly when the organo-HT was freeze dried (log K_{om}
250 TCE=2.37) (Table SM-7). The lower log K_{om} values for dried Mg₃Al-DS are best explained by the
251 lower reactive surface area. This is because drying induces the formation of larger aggregates that
252 during re-suspension in water are not easily broken up (also visible in settling experiments, Fig. SM-
253 7), due to the hydrophobic effect.

254 Based on these initial results, sorption efficiency of organo-HT toward CHC was clearly lower
255 following post-synthesis drying, but less affected by surfactant type. However, seeing that Mg₃Al-DS
256 synthesis is easier and more economical compared to Mg₃Al-1-DF (i.e. room-temperature synthesis,

257 cheaper surfactant), Mg₃Al-DS is clearly a more suitable sorbent. We therefore performed all further
258 sorption experiments with non-dried Mg₃Al-DS.

259

260 3.2.2 Sorption behavior of single CHCs solute systems

261 The hydrophobicity (i.e., water solubility, S_w) amongst CHCs varies (Table SM-1), which ultimately
262 controls the extent by which they can be sorbed by organo-HT (Jobbágy and Regazzoni 2006). For the
263 first time, we determined sorption isotherms for non-dried Mg₃Al-DS in single solute systems with
264 PCE, TCE, CT, TCM, and 1,1,2-TCA shown in Figure 2a (log K_{om} given in Table SM-8). For the
265 CHC types and concentration range ($C_0= 0-400$ mg/L) studied here, the sorption isotherms were linear
266 and log K_{om} values were clearly highest for PCE and lowest for TCM. Plotting the derived log K_{om}
267 values against the respective CHC hydrophobicity showed an inverse linear relationship (Figure 2b),
268 similar to what was observed for aromatic compounds (Jobbágy and Regazzoni, 2006). The
269 previously reported log K_{om} for PCE and TCE sorption by dried Mg₃Al-DS also agree well with these
270 trends (Zhao and Nagy 2004, Fig. 2b), although those were determined for a much lower
271 concentration range (0 to 35 mg/L). The fact that the isotherm was linear over the entire tested CHC
272 concentration range indicates that CHC sorption is controlled by partitioning into the organic
273 interlayer (i.e. organic content OC (%)) rather than by physical adsorption (Chiou et al. 1979; Chiou
274 2002). Similar linear isotherms were also described for sorption of hydrophobic chemicals into
275 organic matter and soils (Delle Site 2001; Karickhoff et al. 1979).

276

277 3.3 Sorption experiment in a ternary solute system

278 To understand more complex, “real-life” systems, we examined the sorption capacity of Mg₃Al-DS in
279 ternary solute systems (TCE, TCM, and 1,1,2-TCA) testing 3 different water chemistry (MilliQ,
280 SGW, and NGW) and varying pH (6-11). TCE, TCM, and 1,1,2-TCA were selected because each
281 represents one of the most common CHCs families (methanes, ethanes, and ethenes) and they share
282 the same number of chlorine atoms.

283

284 3.3.1 Effect of water chemistry

285 All sorption isotherms were linear over the tested CHC concentration range (MilliQ, SGW, and
286 NGW; Figure 3) and $\log K_{om}$ values were similar amongst the three tested waters (Table SM-9).
287 Identical to the single solute system, $\log K_{om}$ values correlated linearly with CHC hydrophobicity
288 (TCE>1,1,2-TCA>TCM). Note however, that absolute $\log K_{om}$ values in ternary solute systems were
289 generally 4-9% lower (Table SM-9) compared to $\log K_{om}$ values in single solute systems (Table SM-
290 8), thus giving a slightly modified linear relationship between $\log K_{om}$ and $\log S_w$ (section 3.4).
291 Overall, these results re-affirmed observations in single solute systems and earlier studies (Jobbágy
292 and Regazzoni, 2006) that solute partitioning is the main mechanism of CHC sorption by Mg_3Al -DS,
293 even if the water matrix is more complex. In addition, we show that sorption does not majorly depend
294 on the co-existence of multiple CHCs (Figure 3), i.e., that the affinity of Mg_3Al -DS towards a specific
295 CHC compound is mainly governed by the CHC hydrophobicity, i.e., water solubility. This also fits
296 with previous work on CHC sorption by soils (Chiou et al., 1983), where it is argued that there is little
297 competitive sorption between the different nonionic organic compounds

298

299 3.3.2 Effect of pH

300 Seeing little difference in $\log K_{om}$ values between the different waters, the effect of pH on Mg_3Al -DS
301 sorption capacity was only investigated for the MilliQ ternary system. The pH range (6 to 11) was
302 chosen based on the stability range reported for Mg_3Al -Cl HT (Jobbágy and Regazzoni 2011) and the
303 pH expected for natural groundwater (pH 6.5-8; Custodio and Llamas 1996). Overall, no significant
304 change in CHC uptake was observed with a change in pH (Figure 4) demonstrating the Mg_3Al -DS
305 compound was stable and kept its sorption capacity over a wide pH range. While no other study has
306 examined pH effects in ternary solute systems, similar insignificant pH effects were also shown for
307 the sorption of acid dye by Mg_2Al -DS (pH 5-9) (Bouraada et al. 2009) and sorption of anionic dye by
308 Mg_2Al -CO₃ (Zhu et al., 2005).

309

310 3.4 Sorption experiments with contaminated groundwater

311 Contaminated groundwater is often far more complex than our ideal laboratory systems, and will
312 include contaminants and conditions that have not been and/or could not be tested in the laboratory.
313 Therefore, it is important to assess the validity of observed relationships, i.e., models, to predict the
314 behavior of newly developed reactants in “real-life” systems before their application at a larger scale.
315 Here we used the observed linear relationship between $\log K_{om}$ and $\log S_w$ from the ternary CHC
316 systems in NGW ($\log K_{om} = -0.50 \cdot \log S_w + 1.58$, $r^2 = 0.97$; Figure 5a) to predict $\log K_{om}$ values for
317 CHCs, whose $\log K_{om}$ values were not determined under laboratory conditions (Table SM-10). Based
318 on these $\log K_{om}$, we then determined the amount of CHCs that should theoretically be removed by
319 Mg_3Al -DS and compared these values to actual CHCs sorption yields measured in the collected
320 contaminated groundwater (Figure 5b, Table SM-10). Overall, there is fairly good agreement between
321 predicted and measured values. Two clear outliers are: 1,1,2-TCA, where the sorption yield was
322 ~44% lower than the predicted value; and TCM, where the yield was ~38% higher than the predicted
323 value. The possibility that the groundwater chemistry impacted these results cannot be excluded and
324 should be investigated further. Overall, our results indicate that the applied linear $\log K_{om}$ - $\log S_w$
325 relationship can predict $\log K_{om}$ for many CHC, but may work less well for others (e.g., TCM, 1,2-
326 TCA) in complex, real groundwater systems.

327

328 **4. Benefits of using organo-HT for decreasing CHCs concentration in contaminated** 329 **groundwater**

330 Activated carbon (AC) is one of the most widely-used sorbent for removal of CHCs from waste
331 streams (Pavoni et al., 2006). The sorption of CHCs onto AC is characterized by a strong solute
332 uptake but non-linear isotherms, which resulted in the ultimate saturation of the sorbent (Smith et al.,
333 1990). Additionally, AC performance is affected by the presence of multiple CHCs (as expected in
334 contaminated groundwater). For example, it has been shown that in binary solute systems there is a
335 clear competition between CHCs for adsorption on AC (Bansal and Goyal 2005). The same sorption

336 mechanism was reported for nonionic organic compounds into cationic clays (Smith and Galan,
337 1995). Organo-clays are similarly effective at sorbing CHC sorbents (compared to the organo-HTs
338 tested in this study and elsewhere (Zhao and Nagy,2004)), and have been proposed for use as a pre-
339 treatment filter material to remove competitive compounds (e.g., aromatic hydrocarbons such as
340 toluene, Alther (2002)) to optimize AC sorption capacity. Based on observations in this study, organo-
341 HT could be used in a similar way (as pre-filters) to optimize the lifetime of fix-bed AC filters and
342 efficiently decrease the concentration of CHCs from aqueous media. These observations include: (a)
343 that the linear relationship between sorption efficiency and the hydrophobicity of the CHC is
344 independent of the size of the CHC molecules, (b) CHC sorption occurs by solute partitioning, i.e., no
345 saturation observed at high concentrations (>400 mg/L), (c) little sorption competition between
346 CHCs in mixtures, (d) easy and low cost Mg₃Al-DS synthesis.

347 It is important to consider that this study determined CHC sorption uptake by organo-HT in different
348 water chemistry, at varying pH, and in the presence of multiple CHCs. However, other variables such
349 as the long-term fate and stability of organo-HT under laboratory and field conditions should be
350 studied next to further evaluate their suitability for remediation applications.

351

352 5. Conclusions

353 The conclusions drawn from the current study are summarized as follows:

- 354 • The intercalation of DS and 1-DF in Mg/Al HT produces hydrophobic nanoparticles that enhance
355 the amount of CHC sorbed in single solute systems. All sorption isotherms were linear and
356 yielded log K_{om} values that correlate inversely with CHCs hydrophobicity (S_w). The linearity of
357 the sorption isotherm demonstrated that the main mechanism of sorption is solute partitioning. In
358 this study, we further showed that this inverse relationship between log K_{om} and S_w is also valid in
359 waters where multiple CHCs are present, confirming that there is little competition between
360 CHCs for sorption by organo-HT.

- 361 • Mg_3Al -DS can be applied as wet paste or as dried nanomaterials depending on the chosen
362 application (e.g. filters, permeable reactive barriers), creating a variety of options for their
363 potential use in groundwater remediation. However, these materials strongly aggregate with
364 drying, decreasing the number of active sorption site. Thus, this aspect and potential
365 modifications to create more porous aggregates should be investigated in future studies.
- 366 • Individually calculated K_{om} values for Mg_3Al -DS and their correlation with S_w were used predict
367 unknown K_{om} in complex contaminated groundwaters. However, it is recommended to carry out
368 specific sorption experiments with selected contaminated groundwater and the present CHCs.

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Figure captions

Figure 1 (a) Sorption isotherms for (a) tetrachloroethylene (PCE) and trichloroethylene (TCE) by Mg_3Al -DS (\blacklozenge , \blacklozenge) and Mg_3Al -1-DF (\blacktriangle , \blacktriangle) as a function of intercalated surfactant anion, (equilibration time: 24 h; pH=9-9.5; $C_i=0-40$ mg/L). (b) Sorption isotherms for trichloroethylene (TCE) by Mg_3Al -DS as a function of various drying processes (Table SM-7) (equilibration time: 24 h; pH=9-9.5; $C_i=0-35$ mg/L). Data points represent the average of duplicate experiments.

Figure 2 (a) Sorption isotherms for a set of chlorinated hydrocarbons in single solute systems by Mg_3Al -DS (added as wet paste; equilibration time 24 h; pH=9-9.5). Data points represent the average of duplicate experiments. (b) Log organic-matter-normalized partition coefficients ($\log K_{om}$) (dm^3/kg) as a function of water solubility, i.e., hydrophobicity, of organic compounds at 25 °C ($\log S_w$ (mol/dm^3)). For comparison, $\log K_{om}$ values reported by Zhao and Nagy 2004 for PCE and TCE sorption by dried Mg_3Al -DS are also shown. PCE: tetrachloroethylene, TCE: trichloroethylene, VC: Vinyl chloride, 1,1-DCE: 1,1 dichloroethylene, cis-DCE: cis-dichloroethylene, trans-DCE: trans- dichloroethylene, 1,1-DCA: 1,1 dichloroethane, 1,2-DCA: 1,2 dichloroethane, 1,1,2-TCA: 1,1,2-trichlorethane.

Figure 3 Sorption isotherms from ternary solute systems (TCE, TCM, and 1,1,2-TCA) for Mg_3Al -DS in (a) MilliQ, (b) natural groundwater, and (c) synthetic groundwater (filled symbols). Lines represent the best fit to the linear regression curves with r^2 values greater than 0.90. Data points represent the average of duplicate experiments. For comparison, sorption data from single solute systems (Fig. 2a) are also shown (unfilled symbols).

Figure 4 Effect of pH on the sorption of CHC in a ternary system (TCE, TCM, and 1,1,2-TCA) by Mg_3Al -DS in MilliQ. ($C_0= 50$ mg/L). (\blacklozenge) trichloroethylene (TCE), (\blacktriangle) trichloromethane (TCM), and (\blacktriangledown) 1,1,2-trichloroethane (1,1,2-TCA). Data points represent the average of duplicate experiments.

Figure 5 (a) Organic-matter-normalized partition coefficients ($\log K_{om}$) (dm^3/kg) as a function of water solubility of organic compounds at 25 °C ($\log S_w$ (mol/dm^3)). Data calculated from sorption isotherms from ternary solute system in NGW (unfilled symbols). Data predicted from $\log K_{om} = -0.50 \cdot \log(S_w) + 1.58$ ($r^2=0.97$) (Filled symbols). (b) Predicted amount sorbed (mg/g) (as derived from Figure 5a) vs experimental amount sorbed (mg/g) calculated from sorption experiments with contaminated groundwater. PCE: tetrachloroethylene, TCE: trichloroethylene, VC: Vinyl chloride, 1,1-DCE: 1,1 dichloroethylene, cis-DCE: cis-dichloroethylene, trans-DCE: trans- dichloroethylene, 1,1-DCA: 1,1 dichloroethane, 1,2-DCA: 1,2 dichloroethane, 1,1,2-TCA: 1,1,2-trichlorethane. (b) Comparison between predicted and experimental amount of individual CHCs sorbed by $\text{Mg}_3\text{Al-DS}$ in NGW.

Table captions

Table 1 Description of sorption experiments performed in this study.

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Table 1

Organo-HT type	Organo-HT treatment	Tested CHC	Tested CHC concentrations (mg/L)	pH	Water Matrix	Results section
Single sorbate system						
Mg ₃ Al-1-DF	Oven dried	PCE or TCE	0-40	9-9.5	MilliQ	3.2.1
Mg ₃ Al-DS	Oven dried	PCE or TCE	0-40	9-9.5	MilliQ	3.2.1
Mg ₃ Al-DS	Oven, freeze dried, not dried	TCE	0-35	9-9.5	MilliQ	3.2.1
Mg ₃ Al-DS	Not dried	PCE, TCE, 1,1,2-TCA, TCM or CT	0-400	9-9.5	MilliQ	3.2.2
Ternary sorbate system						
Mg ₃ Al-DS	Not dried	TCE, TCM, and 1,1,2-TCA	0-150	9-9.5	MilliQ, SGW or NGW	3.3
Mg ₃ Al-DS	Not dried	TCE, TCM, and 1,1,2-TCA	50	-	Varying pH in MilliQ	3.3
Multiple sorbate system						
Mg ₃ Al-DS	Not dried	Multiple CHCs	-	8-9.5	CGW	3.4

PCE: tetrachloroethylene; TCE: trichloroethylene; 1,1,2-TCA: 1,1,2-trichloroethane; TCM: trichloromethane; CHCs: chlorinated hydrocarbons; SGW: synthetic groundwater; NGW: Pristine natural groundwater; CGW: contaminated groundwater.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Graphical abstract

Highlights

- The post-treatment process applied to organo-HT affects its sorption towards CHC.
- Ionic strength and pH have minor effect on the sorption of organo-HT towards CHC.
- Laboratory-calculated K_{om} is used to predict the sorption of CHC in groundwater.